

Under 18 Template

(Suitable for recruitment of young people through intermediaries, such as schools or youth groups)

Thanks for your interest in [... project name...]. In this email, we give you information about our research, as part of our research, and ask for your consent to participate. If you agree, please *reply to this email, stating your name, age and that you agree to the statements in the table below to give your consent*. There's some information for your parent too, later in this message. *So, please copy in your parent or carer in your reply and ask him/her to reply to us, stating their name and whether they agree for you to join our consultation.* 😊

What is the [... state name of the project/ event...] about?

[... in 1 sentence, state what your project/ research/ consultation / interview or focus group is about]

Do I have to take part?

Participation is **voluntary**. There are no bad consequences for you if you decide not to take part in this study. If you decide to take part but then later on you change your mind, you can leave the research and you will not have to explain why. It is absolutely fine if you feel that you don't want to take part in a specific activity or answer specific questions – you can just tell us, and we will move on.

What will happen if I take part?

[Provide details about your research activity. These should include:

- What the nature of participation is (e.g. interview, focus group, workshop, etc)
- If focus group or workshop, what the size of the group (e.g. 4-6 participants)?
- Where is it taking place? Online or in person? If online, which platform do you use (e.g. Zoom, Team etc)
- Overview of your topic guide (e.g. what are you going to ask participants about?)
- Duration of the event
- Is the conversation recorded?
- What will you do with the recording? (Refer to your ethics application.)
- Is anonymity offered? (Give example of what this means in plain English. For example, say: "Nothing you say in the group discussion will be shared with your parents, friends, teachers or school. We will keep your participation anonymous – for example, we will not use your real name or the name of your friends, school, or neighbourhood in our reports. We ask you not to talk later about what **other people** said in the group discussion.")
- If your participants are children or vulnerable people, remember to state your duty of care for them. In our work (which involves children, we said: "Of course, if you tell us anything that suggests you are at risk of harm, we may need to get professional advice, and we'll tell you if we feel we need to do this.")

If you agree to take part in the research, please complete the section below

Your name: (type first name and surname here)

Your age (type here)

Please read these three statements. If you agree with them, put a X in the boxes below	
I have read this message and had the opportunity to ask questions.	
I agree to participate in [... state the type of research activity, i.e., interview, focus group, etc] and for the [... state activity...] to be audio recorded.	
I understand that my responses will be kept confidential and anonymous and that my personal information will be kept securely and destroyed after 5 years.	

This below is the part for parents:

I, parent/guardian, of _____ [insert your child's name here] have read the information above and give consent for my child to participate in the ***Digital Futures Commission's consultation on play in the digital world.***

I also agree for the group discussion to be audio recorded and for the information provided by my child to be used in reports, presentations, and other research outputs.

I understand that my child's participation is entirely voluntary and will not result in any different treatment from the school. I understand that my child does not need to answer any question they do not wish to and can withdraw from the research at any time.

Please type your name here:

Date: _____

Now please email this message back to us, and thanks very much!

PI name, lead researcher: **email**

Researcher name, researcher: **email**

You can read more about our project here: [\[... insert link to your research web page...\]](#)

--- End of Email consent template for under 18 ---

Parental Consent Template

(Suitable for recruitment of young people through parents or legal guardian)

Thanks for your support for [... project name...]. In this email, we give you information about our consultation, as part of our research, and ask for your consent for your child to participate in the consultation. If you agree, please reply to this email, stating your name and that you agree for your child (insert his/her name) to participate in this consultation. 😊

What is the [... state name of the project/ event...] about?

[... in 1 sentence, state what your project/ research/ consultation / interview or focus group is about]

Do I have to take part?

Participation is **voluntary**. There are no bad consequences for you if you decide not to take part in this study. If you decide to take part but then later on you change your mind, you can leave the research and you will not have to explain why. It is absolutely fine if you feel that you don't want to take part in a specific activity or answer specific questions – you can just tell us, and we will move on.

What will happen if I take part?

[Provide details about your research activity. These should include:

- What the nature of participation is (e.g. interview, focus group, workshop, etc)
- If focus group or workshop, what the size of the group (e.g. 4-6 participants)?
- Where is it taking place? Online or in person? If online, which platform do you use (e.g. Zoom, Team etc)
- Overview of your topic guide (e.g. what are you going to ask participants about?)
- Duration of the event
- Is the conversation recorded?
- What will you do with the recording? (Refer to your ethics application.)
- Is anonymity offered? (Give example of what this means in plain English. For example, say: "Nothing you say in the group discussion will be shared with your parents, friends, teachers or school. We will keep your participation anonymous – for example, we will not use your real name or the name of your friends, school, or neighbourhood in our reports. We ask you not to talk later about what **other people** said in the group discussion.")
- If your participants are children or vulnerable people, remember to state your duty of care for them. In our work (which involves children, we said: "Of course, if you tell us anything that suggests you are at risk of harm, we may need to get professional advice, and we'll tell you if we feel we need to do this.")

If you agree for your child(ren) to participate in this research, please complete the section below

Your name: (type first name and surname here)

Your child(ren) name: (type first name and surname here)

Age of your child(ren):

Please read these three statements. If you agree with them, put a X in the boxes below	
I have read this message and had the opportunity to ask questions.	
I agree for my child(ren) to participate in [... state the type of research activity, i.e., interview, focus group, etc] and for the [... state activity...] to be audio recorded.	
I understand that my child(ren) responses will be kept confidential and anonymous and that my personal information will be kept securely and destroyed after 5 years.	

Thanks! Now please email this back to us.

PI name, lead researcher: **email**

Researcher name, researcher: **email**

You can read more about our project here: [... insert link to your research web page...]

--- End of Email parental consent template ---

Over 18 Template

Thanks for your interest in [... project name...]. In this email, we give you information about our consultation, as part of our research, and ask for your consent to participate. If you agree, please reply to this email, stating your name and that you agree to the statements in the table below to give your consent. 😊

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If you agree to take part in the research, please complete the section below

Your name: (type first name and surname here)

Please read these three statements. If you agree with them, put a X in the boxes below	
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I agree to participate in [... state the type of research activity, i.e., interview, focus group, etc] and for the [... state activity...] to be audio recorded.	
I understand that my responses will be kept confidential and anonymous and that my personal information will be kept securely and destroyed after 5 years.	

PI name, lead researcher: **email**

Researcher name, researcher: **email**

You can read more about our project here: [\[... insert link to your research web page... \]](#)

--- End of Email consent template for under 18 ---